

Supplementary Materials: Potential to Enhance Large Scale Molecular Assessments of Skin Photoaging through Virtual Inference of Spatial Transcriptomics from Routine Staining

Supplementary Table 1 Spatial Gene Expression Prediction Performance. AUC, F1, and Spearman values are the macro-averaged (across slides) median (across genes) performance values. AUC and F1-scores are used to measure the performance of the dichotomized expression models, while the Spearman coefficient was used to measure the performance of the continuous expression model. 95% confidence intervals are reported using 1000-sample non-parametric bootstrapping.

Dichotomized Performance						Continuous Performance		
<i>AUC</i>	<i>2.5th</i>	<i>97.5th</i>	<i>F1</i>	<i>2.5th</i>	<i>97.5th</i>	<i>Spearman</i>	<i>2.5th</i>	<i>97.5th</i>
0.795	0.788	0.800	0.614	0.598	0.631	0.600	0.583	0.610

Supplementary Table 2: Extended Performance Pathway Analysis. Combined performance statistics for both the dichotomized and continuous models were used to perform a performance stratified pathway analysis. AUC and Spearman coefficient were used to stratify genes in the dichotomized and continuous tasks, respectively. The top 3 pathways, measured via EnrichR using the Go Biological Process 2023 database, are reported for the highest and lowest performance deciles.

Gene Performance	Task	Pathway	Score	Overlap	P-value
90-100th Percentile Genes	Dichotomized	Establishment of Skin Barrier	2127	6/19	6.9E-10
		Skin Epidermis Development	1785	6/21	4.0E-04
		Keratinocyte Proliferation	803	2/6	1.4E-11
	Continuous	Positive Regulation of Epidermis Development	2725	4/9	7.3E-08
		Desmosome Organization	2654	3/6	2.4E-06
		Intermediate Filament Bundle Assembly	1905	4/7	4.2E-06
80-90th Percentile Genes	Dichotomized	Epidermis Development	733	10/85	1.4E-11
		Intermediate Filament Bundle Assembly	615	2/7	5.1E-4
		Epidermal Cell Differentiation	397	6/54	2.9E-7
	Continuous	Positive Regulation of Triglyceride Catabolic Process	803	2/6	3.6E-4
		Keratinocyte Proliferation	803	2/6	3.6E-4
		Melanin Biosynthetic Process	615	2/7	5.1E-4
70-80th Percentile Genes	Dichotomized	Gap Junction Assembly	803	2/6	3.6E-4
		Glycerol-3-Phosphate Metabolic Process	803	2/6	3.6E-4
		Diacylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	615	2/7	5.1E-4
	Continuous	Regulation Of Mast Cell Chemotaxis	1125	2/5	2.5E-4
		Gap Junction Assembly	803	2/6	3.7E-4
		Positive Regulation of Blood Vessel Endothelial Cell Proliferation Involved In Sprouting Angiogenesis	494	2/8	3.7E-4
60-70th Percentile Genes	Dichotomized	Cholesterol Biosynthetic Process	826	5/25	1.4E-7

		Negative Regulation of Neural Precursor Cell Proliferation	615	2/7	5.1E-4
		Secondary Alcohol Biosynthetic Process	499	4/24	5.8E-6
	Continuous	Leucine Metabolic Process	803	2/6	3.7E-4
		Negative Regulation of Phospholipase Activity	615	2/7	5.1E-4
		Smooth Muscle Tissue Development	408	2/9	8.7E-4
50-60th Percentile Genes	Dichotomized	Vascular Wound Healing	803	2/6	3.7E-4
		Leukocyte Aggregation	615	2/7	5.1E-4
		Regulation of Mesenchymal Stem Cell Differentiation	615	2/7	5.1E-4
	Continuous	Glomerulus Vasculature Development	1125	2/5	2.5E-4
		Plasma Membrane Raft Organization	1125	2/5	2.5E-4
		Fatty Acid Elongation, Monounsaturated Fatty Acid	803	2/6	3.7E-4
40-50th Percentile Genes	Dichotomized	Humoral Immune Response Mediated by Circulating Immunoglobulin	1125	2/5	2.5E-4
		Cell Junction Disassembly	1125	2/5	2.5E-4
		Positive Regulation of Vascular Associated Smooth Muscle Cell Differentiation	1125	2/5	2.5E-4
	Continuous	Regulation Of Vascular Wound Healing	615	2/7	5.1E-4
		Hepoxilin Metabolic Process	615	2/7	5.1E-4
		Hepoxilin Biosynthetic Process	615	2/7	5.1E-4
30-40th Percentile Genes	Dichotomized	SREBP Signaling Pathway	615	2/7	5.1E-4
		Cellular Response to Sterol Depletion	493	2/8	6.8E-4
		Regulation Of Epithelial Cell Differentiation	380	3/18	9.4E-5
	Continuous	Negative Regulation of Platelet Activation	505	3/15	5.3E-5
		Negative Regulation of Platelet Aggregation	494	2/8	6.8E-4
		Alpha-Linolenic Acid Metabolic Process	408.7	2/9	8.7E-4
20-30th Percentile Genes	Dichotomized	Cyclooxygenase Pathway	494	2/8	6.8E-4
		Regulation of Tumor Necrosis Factor Superfamily Cytokine Production	494	2/9	6.8E-4
		Regulation Of Adipose Tissue Development	299	2/11	1.3E-3
	Continuous	Monoacylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	803	2/6	3.7E-4
		Metanephric Nephron Tubule Development	803	2/6	3.7E-4
		Lipid Oxidation	634	3/13	3.3E-5
	Dichotomized	Leukocyte Apoptotic Process	1125	2/5	2.5E-4

10-20th Percentile Genes		T-helper 17 Cell Lineage Commitment	615	2/7	5.1E-4
		Long-Chain fatty-acyl-CoA Metabolic Process	533	4/23	4.8E-6
	Continuous	Establishment Of Lymphocyte Polarity	1125	2/5	2.5E-4
		Positive Regulation of Dendritic Cell Antigen Processing and Presentation	1125	2/5	2.5E-4
		Positive Regulation of Antigen Processing and Presentation	1125	2/5	2.5E-4
0-10th Percentile Genes	Dichotomized	Interleukin-2-Mediated Signaling Pathway	615	2/7	2.8E-4
		Cellular Response to Interleukin-2	615	2/7	5.1E-4
		Negative Regulation of T Cell Apoptotic Process	615	2/7	5.1E-4
	Continuous	Gas Transport	504	3/15	5.3E-5
		Positive Regulation of Respiratory Burst	493	2/8	6.7E-4
		Regulation Of Skeletal Muscle Cell Differentiation	493	2/8	6.7E-4

Supplementary Table 3: Histological Pathway Analysis for Dichotomized Expression. The top 100 differentially expressed genes for each cluster were established via the Wilcoxon test. These genes were then analyzed using *EnrichR* and the Go Biological Process 2023 database to find the top 10 most salient biological pathways as measured by magnitude and statistical significance (i.e., combined score). These pathways are reported for both the predicted and ground truth data. Bolded pathways are shared between both predicted and ground truth data. Results for sample 14 are displayed for brevity.

<i>Histology</i>	Ground Truth		Predicted		<i>Overlap</i>	<i>P</i>
	<i>Pathway</i>	<i>Overlap</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>Pathway</i>		
Eccrine Gland	Positive Regulation of Vascular Associated Smooth Muscle Cell Differentiation	2/5	2.4E-4	Vascular Wound Healing	2/6	3.6E-4
	Venous Blood Vessel Morphogenesis	2/5	2.4E-4	Angiogenesis Involved in Wound Healing	2/10	1.1E-3
	Glomerular Epithelial Cell Differentiation	2/5	2.4E-4	Response To Prostaglandin E	2/10	1.1E-3
	Response To Heparin	2/5	2.4E-4	Long-Chain Fatty-Acyl-CoA Metabolic Process	3/23	2.0E-4
				Very Long-Chain Fatty Acid Biosynthetic Process	2/12	1.6E-3
	Renal Filtration Cell Differentiation	2/5	2.4E-4	Fatty Acid Elongation	2/12	1.6E-3
	Regulation Of Fatty Acid Oxidation	4/16	1.0E-6	Monoacylglycerol Metabolic Process	2/13	1.9E-3
	Vascular Associated Smooth Muscle Cell Development	2/6	3.6E-4	Lipid Oxidation	2/13	1.9E-3
	Smooth Muscle Tissue Development	2/9	8.7E-4	Fatty-Acyl-CoA Biosynthetic Process	3/25	2.6E-4
	Intracellular Sodium Ion Homeostasis	3/18	9.4E-5			
Mast Cell Degranulation	2/10	1.1E-3	Smooth Muscle Contraction	2/14	2.2E-3	
Epidermis	Keratinocyte Differentiation	7/42	1.5E-9	Melanin Biosynthetic Process	2/7	5.1E-4
	Establishment Of Skin Barrier	4/19	2.2E-6	Lipoxygenase Pathway	2/7	5.1E-4
	Lipoxygenase Pathway	2/7	5.1E-4	Hepoxilin Metabolic Process	2/7	5.1E-4
	Hepoxilin Metabolic Process	2/7	5.1E-4	Hepoxilin Biosynthetic Process	2/7	5.1E-4

	Hepoxilin Biosynthetic Process	2/7	5.1E-4	Keratinocyte Differentiation	6/42	6.1E-8
	Skin Epidermis Development	4/21	3.3E-6	Epidermal Cell Differentiation	6/54	2.9E-7
	Epidermal Cell Differentiation	7/54	9.2E-9	Phenol-Containing Compound Biosynthetic Process	2/10	1.1E-3
	Skin Development	8/68	1.7E-9	Epidermis Development	7/85	2.3E-7
	Peptide Cross-Linking	4/27	9.5E-6	Antibacterial Humoral Response	5/49	4.5E-6
	Negative Regulation of Peptidase Activity	6/60	5.4E-7	Skin Development	6/68	1.1E-6
Hair Follicle	Cell Junction Disassembly	2/5	2.5E-4	Alpha-Linolenic Acid Metabolic Process	3/9	1.0E-5
	Humoral Immune Response Mediated by Circulating Immunoglobulin Response To Heparin	2/5	2.5E-4	Monoacylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	2/6	3.7E-4
	Positive Regulation of Fibroblast Apoptotic Process	2/6	3.7E-4	Fatty Acid Elongation, Saturated Fatty Acid	2/6	3.7E-4
	Melanin Biosynthetic Process	2/7	5.1E-4	Fatty Acid Elongation, Monounsaturated Fatty Acid	2/6	3.7E-4
	Synapse Pruning	2/8	6.8E-4	Fatty Acid Elongation, Polyunsaturated Fatty Acid	2/6	3.7E-4
	Regulation Of Fibroblast Apoptotic Process	2/8	6.8E-4	Negative Regulation of Dendritic Cell Apoptotic Process	2/6	3.7E-4
	Intermediate Filament Organization	7/68	4.8E-8	Fatty Acid Elongation, Unsaturated Fatty Acid	2/6	3.7E-4
	Positive Regulation of Mesenchymal Cell Proliferation	2/9	8.7E-4	Positive Regulation of Neutrophil Chemotaxis	4/18	1.7E-6
	Very-Low-Density Lipoprotein Particle Assembly	2/10	1.0E-3	Fatty Acid Elongation	3/12	2.6E-5
Lymphatic /Vascular	Regulation Of Muscle System Process	3/11	1.9E-5	Very Long-Chain Fatty Acid Biosynthetic Process	3/12	2.6E-5
	Regulation Of Vascular Associated Smooth Muscle Cell Migration	3/12	2.6E-5	Vascular Wound Healing	3/6	2.4E-6
	Negative Regulation of Nitric Oxide Biosynthetic Process	2/7	5.1E-4	Positive Regulation of Extrinsic Apoptotic Signaling Pathway Via Death Domain Receptors	2/5	2.5E-4
	Negative Regulation of Nitric Oxide Metabolic Process	2/7	5.1E-4	Angiogenesis Involved in Wound Healing	3/10	1.4E-5
	T-helper 17 Cell Lineage Commitment	2/7	5.1E-4	T-helper 17 Cell Lineage Commitment	2/7	5.1E-4
	Smooth Muscle Contraction	3/14	4.2E-5	Negative Regulation of Platelet Activation	3/15	5.3E-4
	Negative Regulation of Smooth Muscle Cell Migration	3/14	4.2E-5	T-helper 17 Cell Differentiation	2/8	6.8E-4
	Extracellular Structure Organization	10/109	1.7E-10	Negative Regulation of Platelet Aggregation	2/8	6.8E-4
	Skin Morphogenesis	2/8	6.8E-4	Negative Regulation of Vascular Associated Smooth Muscle Cell Proliferation	3/17	7.8E-5
	T-helper 17 Cell Differentiation	2/8	6.8E-4	Negative Regulation of Lipid Localization	2/9	8.7E-4
Sebaceous Gland	Acylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	6/22	9.4E-10	T-helper Cell Lineage Commitment	2/10	1.1E-3
	Unsaturated Fatty Acid Biosynthetic Process	3/8	6.7E-6	Unsaturated Fatty Acid Biosynthetic Process	6.7E-6	3/8
	Alpha-Linolenic Acid Metabolic Process	3/9	1.0E-5	Alpha-Linolenic Acid Metabolic Process	1.0E-5	3/9
	Long-Chain Fatty-Acyl-CoA Metabolic Process	5/23	8.8E-8	Acylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	7.0E-8	5/22
	Triglyceride Biosynthetic Process	4/17	1.3E-6	Long-Chain Fatty-Acyl-CoA Metabolic Process	8.8E-8	5/23
				Fatty Acid Elongation: Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids	3.7E-4	2/6

Macrophage Derived Foam Cell Differentiation	2/6	3.7E-4	Fatty Acid Elongation: Saturated Fatty Acid	3.7E-4	2/6
Fatty Acid Elongation: Monounsaturated Fatty Acids	2/6	3.7E-4	Fatty Acid Elongation: Unsaturated Fatty Acid	3.7E-4	2/6
Fatty Acid Elongation: Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids	2/6	3.7E-4	Monoacylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	3.7E-4	2/6
Fatty Acid Elongation: Unsaturated Fatty Acids	2/6	3.7E-4	Fatty Acid Elongation: Monounsaturated Fatty Acids	3.7E-4	2/6
Fatty Acid Elongation: Saturated Fatty Acids	2/6	3.7E-4	Very Long-Chain Fatty Acid Biosynthetic Process	2.6E-5	3/12

Supplementary Figure 1: Continuous RNA Expression Prediction. Continuous spatial gene expression was inferred for (A) samples 107 and (B) 178 and compared with their respective ground truths. The higher gene expression values are displayed in yellow, while lower values are shown in purple. Performance is displayed for

several top performing genes, including KRT14, CXCL14, and PI16, which achieved macro-averaged Spearman coefficients of 0.849, 0.846, and 0.822.

Supplementary Figure 2: Log Expression Topological Analysis. (A) From left to right, ground truth spatial Leiden clustering, ground truth aligned UMAP, and predicted aligned UMAP for sample 107. (B) From left to right, ground truth spatial Leiden clustering, ground truth aligned UMAP, and predicted aligned UMAP for sample 167. In both rows, the same spots are colored identically according to their ground truth gene expression profiles after Leiden clustering analysis. Log-transformed gene expression data was used here. The Leiden clustering resolution was set to 0.2.

Supplementary Figure 3: Dichotomized Expression Spatial Leiden Clustering. Visium spots were clustered according to their dichotomized gene expression profiles using both the ground truth and synthetic data for samples **(A)** 14 and **(B)** 178 and visualized spatially. Note that there is no relationship between clusters in the predicted and ground truth cases. A Leiden clustering resolution of 0.2 was used.

Supplementary Figure 4: Log Expression Spatial Leiden Clustering. Visium spots were clustered according to their log transformed gene expression profiles using both the ground truth and synthetic data for samples **(A)** 107 and **(B)** 167 and visualized spatially. Note that there is no relationship between clusters in the predicted and ground truth cases. A Leiden clustering resolution of 0.2 was used.

Supplementary Table 4: Histological Pathway Analysis for Continuous Expression. The top 100 differentially expressed genes for each cluster were established via the Wilcoxon test. These genes were then analyzed using EnrichR and the Go Biological Pathways database to find the top 10 most salient pathways as measured by combined scores. These pathways are reported for both the predicted and ground truth data. Bolded pathways are shared between both predicted and ground truth data. Results for sample 14 are displayed for brevity.

Ground Truth				Predicted		
<i>Histology</i>	<i>Pathway</i>	<i>Overlap</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>Pathway</i>	<i>Overlap</i>	<i>P</i>
Eccrine Gland	Renal Filtration Cell Differentiation	2/5	2.5E-4	Humoral Immune Response Mediated by Circulating Immunoglobulin	2/5	2.5E-4
	Response To Heparin	2/5	2.5E-4	Cell Junction Disassembly	2/5	2.5E-4

	Glomerular Epithelial Cell Differentiation	2/5	2.5E-4	Regulation Of Adipose Tissue Development	3/11	1.9E-5
	Regulation Of Fatty Acid Oxidation	4/16	1.0E-5	SREBP Signaling Pathway	2/7	5.1E-4
	Positive Regulation of Mesenchymal Cell Proliferation	2/9	8.7E-4	Lipid Biosynthetic Process	8/71	2.4E-9
	Intracellular Sodium Ion Homeostasis	3/18	9.4E-5	Long-Chain Fatty-Acyl-CoA Metabolic Process	4/23	4.8E-6
	Negative Regulation of Lymphocyte Migration	2/10	1.1E-3	Tricarboxylic Acid Metabolic Process	2/8	6.8E-4
	Mast Cell Activation Involved in Immune Response	2/10	1.1E-3	Synapse Pruning	2/8	6.8E-4
	Mast Cell Degranulation		1.1E-3	Cellular Response to Sterol Depletion	2/8	6.8E-4
	Regulation Of Mesenchymal Cell Proliferation	2/11	1.3E-3	Positive Regulation of Fatty Acid Metabolic Process	3/17	7.8E-5
Epidermis	Keratinocyte Proliferation	3/6	2.4E-6	Melanin Biosynthetic Process	4/7	2.0E-8
	Peptide Cross-Linking	7/27	5.2E-11	Keratinocyte Proliferation	3/6	2.4E-6
	Positive Regulation Of Epidermis Development	3/9	1.0E-5	Establishment Of Skin Barrier	5/19	3.1E-8
	Negative Regulation Of Peptidase Activity	9/60	1.6E-11	Skin Epidermis Development	5/21	5.4E-8
	Epidermis Development	10/85	1.4E-11	Phenol-Containing Compound Biosynthetic Process	3/10	1.4E-5
	Establishment Of Skin Barrier	4/19	2.2E-6	Peptide Cross-Linking	5/27	2.1E-7
	Hepoxilin Biosynthetic Process	2/7	5.1E-4	Hepoxilin Biosynthetic Process	2/7	5.1E-4
	Lipoxygenase Pathway	2/7	5.1E-4	Lipoxygenase Pathway	2/7	5.1E-4
	Hepoxilin Metabolic Process	2/7	5.1E-4	Hepoxilin Metabolic Process	2/7	5.1E-4
	Skin Epidermis Development	4/21	3.3E-6	Negative Regulation of Peptidase Activity	7/60	2.0E-8
Hair Follicle	Response To Heparin	2/5	2.5E-4	Intermediate Filament Organization	12/68	7.1E-16
	Positive Regulation of Fibroblast Apoptotic Process	2/6	3.7E-4	Negative Regulation of Dendritic Cell Apoptotic Process	2/6	3.7E-4
	Gap Junction Assembly	2/6	3.7E-4	Regulation of Dendritic Cell Apoptotic Process	2/9	8.7E-4
	Positive Regulation of Kidney Development	2/6	3.7E-4	Positive Regulation of Neutrophil Chemotaxis	43/18	9.4E-5
	Tooth Mineralization	2/7	5.1E-4	Response To Prostaglandin E	2/10	1.1E-3
	Regulation of Transforming Growth Factor Beta Activation	2/7	5.1E-4	Supramolecular Fiber Organization	16/316	4.2E-12
	Skin Morphogenesis	2/8	6.8E-4	Positive Regulation of Granulocyte Chemotaxis	3/21	1.5E-4
	Regulation of Fibroblast Apoptotic Process	2/8	6.8E-4	Response To Nitric Oxide	2/11	1.3E-3
	Positive Regulation of Glial Cell Differentiation	3/17	7.8E-5	Negative Regulation of Leukocyte Apoptotic Process	2/11	1.3E-3
	Positive Regulation of Mesenchymal Cell Proliferation	2/9	8.7E-4	Positive Regulation of Neutrophil Migration	3/23	2.0E-4
Lymphatic /Vascular	Regulation Of Muscle System Process	3/11	1.9E-5	Glomerulus Vasculature Development	2/5	2.5E-4

	Regulation Of Vascular Associated Smooth Muscle Cell Migration	3/12	2.6E-5	Negative Regulation of Intracellular Transport	2/7	5.1E-4
	Regulation off Muscle Contraction	5/29	3.0E-7	Cellular Response to Leptin Stimulus	2/7	5.1E-4
	Negative Regulation of Nitric Oxide Metabolic Process	2/7	5.1E-4	Positive Regulation of Extracellular Matrix Disassembly	2/7	5.1E-4
	T-helper 17 Cell Lineage Commitment	2/7	5.1E-4	Negative Regulation of Platelet Aggregation	2/8	6.8E-4
	Negative Regulation of Intracellular Transport	2/7	5.1E-4	Response To Leptin	2/8	6.8E-4
	Negative Regulation of Nitric Oxide Biosynthetic Process	2/7	5.1E-4	Skin Morphogenesis	2/8	6.8E-4
	Smooth Muscle Contraction	3/14	4.2E-5	Integrin Activation	2/8	6.8E-4
	Negative Regulation of Smooth Muscle Cell Migration	3/14	4.2E-5	Regulation Of Cell Killing	2/8	6.8E-4
	Cyclooxygenase Pathway	2/8	6.8E-4	Cellular Response to Glucocorticoid Stimulus	3/17	7.8E-5
Sebaceous Gland	Cholesterol Biosynthetic Process	9/25	2.6E-15	Long-Chain fatty-acyl-CoA Metabolic Process	8/23	1.4E-13
	Long-Chain fatty-acyl-CoA Metabolic Process	8/23	1.4E-13	Cholesterol Biosynthetic Process	8/25	3.0E-13
	Secondary Alcohol Biosynthetic Process	8/24	2.0E-13	Alpha-Linolenic Acid Metabolic Process	4/9	7.3E-8
	Alpha-Linolenic Acid Metabolic Process	4/9	7.3E-8	Monoacylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	3/6	2.4E-6
	Monoacylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	3/6	2.4E-6	Acylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	7/22	1.0E-11
	Acylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	7/22	1.0E-11	Secondary Alcohol Biosynthetic Process	7/24	2.0E-11
	Sterol Biosynthetic Process	8/28	8.4E-13	Diacylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	3/7	4.2E-6
	Diacylglycerol Biosynthetic Process	3/7	4.2E-6	Sterol Biosynthetic Process	7/28	6.9E-11
	Fatty Acid Elongation	4/12	2.8E-7	Fatty Acid Elongation	4/12	2.8E-7
	Triglyceride Biosynthetic Process	5/17	1.7E-8	Long-Chain fatty-acyl-CoA Biosynthetic Process	5/17	1.7E-8

Supplementary Figure 5: Log Expression Histological Analysis. Aligned-UMAP procedure was used to reduce the dimensionality of both the ground truth and predicted dichotomized gene expression vectors for **(A)** sample 107 and **(B)** sample 167. Spots are colored according to their histological annotations.